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ANALYSIS OF SURFACE EMG USING SECOND AND THIRD- ORDER STATISTICS/SPECTRA – BASED PARAMETERS

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Abstract: The objective of this ongoing study is to investigate if surface electromyography signals (SEMG), could be characterized using bispectrum and third-order statistics/spectra (HOS) – based parameters. In particular, the bicoherence index was used for measuring the degree of Gaussianity of the signal. The linearity of the signal, based on deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant, together with the amplitude of the bispectrum, its coordinates and its variance from the peak were estimated. Power spectrum and time domain parameters were also estimated. Experimental results from the analysis of real SEMG data recorded from thirty-three adult normal subjects (13 female and 20 male) aged between 20 and 50 years old, proved an influence of contraction on the aforementioned parameters ($p < 0.05$). Further work is currently in progress in order to evaluate the usefulness of HOS in subjects suffering from neuromuscular disorders.

Index terms: Surface electromyography, Bispectral analysis, Power spectrum analysis.

Introduction

Analysis of physiological signals using Power Spectrum (PS) techniques has been a well-accepted method for the last few decades. Due to the limitations though to: (i) detect and characterize existing non linearities of the signal, (ii) estimate the phase, and (iii) extract information due to deviations from normality [1], Higher Order Statistics (HOS), have been introduced in the 1960's and applied in the 1970's. Early attempts to use these in physiological signals have been reported and applied in electroencephalogram (EEG), with promising results [2]. Since now, no attempts have been made, however, to utilize HOS in electromyography signals and, in particular, in surface electromyography signals (SEMG).

This study analyses the influence of transition from 10% to 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC), of thirty-three analyzed recorded SEMG on seven parameters of the bifrequency domain of

bispectrum, four of the frequency domain of PS and two of the time domain.

Materials and Methods

Data Capture. SEMG were recorded from the biceps brachii (BB) muscle of forty-six normal subjects (28 male and 18 female), aged between 5 and 60 years old. The subjects were divided in age groups per decade. i.e., 3 subjects ≤ 10 yrs, 11 yrs ≤ 7 subjects ≤ 20 yrs, 21 yrs ≤ 19 subjects ≤ 30 yrs, 31 yrs ≤ 8 subjects ≤ 40 yrs, 41 yrs ≤ 6 subjects ≤ 50 yrs, and 51 yrs ≤ 3 subjects ≤ 60 yrs. Recording was done using a four-bar EMG active probe with an interelectrode distance of 10 mm and a bar width of 1 mm. The electrode block was placed on the BB (see Fig. 1), in such a way so that the second electrode was at a distance equal with $1/3$ of the BB length towards the shoulder, although exact positioning was quite difficult for female subjects and children.

Figure 1: Positioning of the electrode block on the BB. The 2nd electrode was placed at a distance equal to $1/3$ x towards the shoulder.

A bar configuration has been preferred from the well-accepted circular configuration, since the former intersects with more fibers than the latter. By intersecting more fibers a greater amplitude will be recorded [3]. From the four bars of the electrode, the second was used as allocation index. Its predefined placement ensures that all four electrodes lay between the innervation zone of the motor unit and the tendon. The differential recordings were recorded simultaneously one from each pair of the electrode bars. Only the highest value though of the pair was used for this analysis. Both pairs will be needed in the future if muscle fiber conduction velocity (MFCV) is to be estimated. Recordings were performed for 5 seconds at 10%, 30%, 50%, 70% and 100% of the maximum voluntary contraction (MVC). An antialiasing band pass filter [20÷500Hz] was initially applied on the recorded signals, which were then sampled with a sampling frequency of 1000Hz at a 12-bit digitization resolution. Furthermore, the skin temperature was noted, since it has been verified that the mean frequency or the mean power frequency of the EMG signal decreases with a reduction in muscle temperature [4].

Time domain analysis. Two parameters were estimated from the analysis of SEMGs in the time domain. In particular, the number of turns was defined as the number of slope reversals separated from the previous and the following turn by an amplitude difference greater than 50 μ V. The number of zero crossings per second was defined as the number of sign reversals exceeding a threshold of 50 μ V.

Power spectral analysis. The following measures were estimated from the power spectrum curve of the analyzed SEMGs: median frequency f_p , frequency at max power f_{pmax} , max power P_{max} , and total power P_{total} . The signal was segmented at 512 points with 25% overlap.

Bispectral analysis. For a zero-mean, stationary process $\{X(k)\}$, the third-order cumulant (TOC) is defined as the expected value of the triple product

$$R(m, n) = E\{X(k)X(k+m)X(k+n)\}, (1)$$

and the bispectrum is defined as the Fourier transform of the TOC sequence [5]:

$$B(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{n=\infty} R(m, n) e^{-j(\omega_1 m + \omega_2 n)}. (2)$$

In addition, the sum of magnitudes of the estimated bispectrum is computed by

$$D = \sum_{(\omega_1, \omega_2)} |B(\omega_1, \omega_2)|. (3)$$

To quantify the non-Gaussianity of a random process, the normalized bispectrum, or bicoherence is estimated as follows

$$B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{B(\omega_1, \omega_2)}{\sqrt{P(\omega_1)P(\omega_2)P(\omega_1 + \omega_2)}}, (4)$$

where $P(\cdot)$ is the power spectrum. The test of Gaussianity is based on the mean bicoherence power defined as follows

$$S_g = \sum |B_n(\omega_1, \omega_2)|, (5)$$

with the summation performed over the non-redundant region.

The Gaussianity test (actually zero-skewness test) basically involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is zero. The linearity test involves deciding whether or not the estimated bicoherence is constant in the bifrequency domain, employing a measure of the difference (dR) between a theoretical and an estimated inter-quartile range R .

The Bispectral analysis was performed with Hispec toolkit of MATLAB 5.3 (Mathworks Inc). The signal was segmented into overlapped records, for reducing the variance of the estimated BS, using a window of 512 points in length with a 25% overlap. The analysis for the Gaussianity test was accepted if the probability of false alarm, was less than 5%. The linearity analysis was accepted if the difference between the estimated statistic R was not more than a factor of two difference than the inter-quartile range of $X^2_2(\lambda)$ (the X^2 distributed random variable, with 2 degrees of freedom and non-centrality parameter, λ).

Results and Discussion

The results presented in this paper correspond to those derived from adults only (20 to 50 years old), thus from 33 subjects. Figure 2, illustrates the PS, a plot of the singular values and a plot of the BS of a female subject aged 21 yrs, recorded at 100% of MVC. From the power spectrum plot, the median frequency, the frequency at maximum power, the maximum power and the total power were estimated. From the bispectrum plots, the amplitude of the peak is estimated, B_{max} , its coordinates and its variation from the peak in both directions x and y were also estimated.

Figure 2: Plots of PS, Singular values and BS of a female subject aged 21yrs recorded at 100% of MVC. Frequency axis of the PS and the BS plots should be multiplied by 1000 to give values in Hz.

Results extracted from the SEMGs of the 33 normal subjects are shown in Table 1. These have been used to investigate whether or not there is a significant difference in the change of the mean of the 13 parameters extracted. Table 2 indicates the influence of transition from one level of voluntary contraction to another for all thirteen parameters investigated. Differences in the means of parameters were evaluated using the Wilcoxon matched pairs rank test. A two-tailed 5% significance level was utilized.

Results show a significant change in both parameters of the time domain, i.e., the number of turns per second and number of zero crossings for any contraction transition.

The analysis in the PS domain gave also straightforward results. The median frequency variation is significant for transitions from low to high and from mid to high force levels. Shankar *et al.* [6] have also shown a variation in median frequency with an increase in applied torque. The frequency however, where maximum Power occurs, stays fairly constant irrespective of the force level, as shown in Table 1. The maximum and total power, though, show a steadily increase, which has also been reported by Li [7] Analysis in the BS domain is though more complicated. The amplitude change of the peak in a BS plot, between 10% of the MVC and any other percentage is significant. Any other transition though gave non-significant indexes. The change in the position of Bmax in either direction for any of the 10 different transitions is non significant. The change in the spreading of the peak in the x direction seems to change significantly from low to high FL, from mid to high FL and also between the two mid FL (50 and 70%). The only significant FL given for the spreading of the maximum peak of the bispectrum in the y-direction was from 30 to 50%. The test of the bicoherence index (test of Gaussianity) showed a significant difference between low and high FL and also between mid and high FL. Similar findings have been reported for needle EMG recordings [8]. Finally a test on deciding whether or not the bicoherence index was constant or not (test of linearity), showed a significant change between transitions 10 to 30%, 10 and 100% and 70 to 100%. It must be noted that 12.1 % of the recordings failed the Gaussianity criteria and 18.2% failed the Linearity criteria.

Table 1. Average parameters for 33 normal subjects aged between 21 and 50 years old.

Parameters	Percentage of Force Levels				
	10	30	50	70	100
Turns/second (t/s)	7	19	34	51	72
Zero crossings (crossings)	3	11	23	34	56
Median frequency (f_p)	102	99	100	98	96
Frequency at max power (f_x)	72	73	78	73	72
Maximum power (P_{max})	3E-09	2E-08	6E-08	2E-07	6E-07
Total power (P_{total})	9E-08	5E-07	1E-06	3E-06	1E-05
Amplitude of Bispectrum (B_{max})	442	969	513	957	11325
Test of Gaussianity (Gaussianity)	251	253	252	239	311
Test of Linearity (Linearity)	1.34	1.93	1.75	1.53	2.24
Bmax coordinate in x-direction (f₁)	52	52	53	54	53
Bmax coordinate in y-direction (f₂)	34	39	39	37	37
Spreading of Bmax in x-direction (f_{1var})	60	58	59	54	52
Spreading of Bmax in y-direction (f_{2var})	14	14	15	15	15

Table 2. Evaluation of the transition from a lower to a higher percentage of the force level as a significant (S) ($p < 0.05$) or not significant (NS) ($p \geq 0.05$) factor for the 13 parameters investigated using the Wilcoxon paired two-tailed test.

Parameter	10/30	10/50	10/70	10/100	30/50	30/70	30/100	50/70	50/100	70/100
t/s	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
Crossings	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
F_p	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
f_x	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
P_{max}	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
P_{total}	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S
B_{max}	S	S	S	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Gaussianity	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	S
Linearity	S	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	S
f_1	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
f_2	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
f_{1var}	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	S	S	S	NS
f_{2var}	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Conclusions

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of force level on 13 different parameters extracted from surface electromyography signals recorded from the BB muscle of 33 normal subjects. Emphasis was given on Higher-Order Statistics since they may overcome limitations present in Power Spectral analysis.

Results showed that the influences of force transition from a low to a high level are quite obvious and clear in all time domain and frequency domain parameters. This also applies to most Bispectrum parameters.

In the near future these findings will be compared with those taken from signals recorded from patients suffering with neuromuscular diseases, aiming to replace, even partly, needle EMG examinations, necessary for the assessment of neuromuscular diseases.

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References

[1] C. L. Nikias and M. R. Raghuveer, "Bispectrum estimation: A digital signal processing framework," *Proc. IEEE*, Vol. 75, pp. 869-891, 1987.
[2] J.C. Sigl and N. S. Chamoun., "An introduction to Bispectral analysis for the electroencephalogram," *Journal of Clinical monitoring*, Vol. 10, No. 6, pp 392-404, 1994.

[3] C. J. De Luca, "Surface electromyography. Detection and recording," *A publication by the Neuromuscular Research Center*, Boston University, 1995.
[4] R. Merletti, M. A. Sabbahi and C. J. De Luca., "Median frequency of the myoelectric signal. Effects of muscle ischemia and cooling," *Eur. J. Applied Physiology*, Vol. 52, pp. 258, 1984.
[5] M. J. Hinich, "Testing for Gaussianity and Linearity of a stationary time series," *J. Time and Series analysis*, Vol. 3, pp. 169-176, 1982.
[6] S. Shankkar, R. E. Gander and B. R. Brandell, "Changes in myoelectric signal (MES) power spectra during dynamic contractions" *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 73: 142-150, 1989.
[7] W. Li and K. Sakamoto, "The influence of location on muscle fiber conduction velocity and EMG power spectrum during voluntary isometric contraction measured with surface array electrodes," *Applied Human Science, Journal of Physiological Anthropology*, Vol. 15, No. 1, pp. 25-32, 1996.
[8] C. S. Pattichis, S. Spyrou, R. Constantinou, C. N. Schizas and L. T. Middleton., "Bispectral analysis of the EMG Interference Pattern: Preliminary findings," in *Proc. of the Int. Conf. on Digital Signal Processing*, July 14-16, pp. 298-303, 1993.